

ENVIRONMENTAL DATA SERVICES

WEATHER SERVICES AND PRODUCTS FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

ENVIROMet.

Helping to improve the environment

The Met. Office

rep.00091

AIR POLLUTION RELATED PACKAGES

Current Price List (1) April 1994

Product	Brief Description	Price
Data For Dispersion Models	Normalised Percentage Frequency Analysis of wind direction, wind speed and Pasquill Stability Category.	£390 + VAT
	Data-set of specific hourly Meteorological Parameters together with morning and afternoon Mixing Heights for direct input.	£390 + VAT
	Data-set of specific hourly Meteorological Parameters together with rural and urban Mixing Heights for direct input.	£390 + VAT
Climatological Summary	Analysis of means and extreme values of selected weather parameters.	
	Long Period Analysis Short Period Analysis (up to 10 years)	£150 + VAT £100 + VAT
Basic Pasquill Stability Category Analysis	Frequency Analysis of Pasquill Stability Category as a function of hours and months.	£120 + VAT
Pasquill Stability Analysis	Frequency Analysis of Pasquill Stability Category as a function of hours, months wind speed and direction.	£250 + VAT
Boundary Layer Depth Analysis	Frequency Analysis of Boundary Layer depth and Pasquill Stability Category as a function of hours and months as well as a Frequency Analysis of Pasquill Stability as a function of hours, months, wind speed and direction.	£320 + VAT
Pasquill Stability & Boundary Layer depth Analysis	Frequency of each Stability Category as a function of Boundary Layer Thickness for each month and for the whole year.	£180 + VAT

AIR POLLUTION RELATED PACKAGES

Current Price List (2) April 1994

Product	Brief Description	Price
Average Boundary Layer Thickness Analysis	Average Boundary Layer Thickness as a function of wind speed and Stability Category for each month and for the whole year.	£180 + VAT
UK - ADMS	Frequency Analysis of Wind Speed and Direction, Surface Sensible Heat Flux, Boundary Layer Depth and Precipitation for specified hours, months and years. Formatted as appropriate for input into the UK Atmospheric Dispersion Modelling System (UK-ADMS).	£390 + VAT
	Hourly Data Analysis for a period of 1 year for direct input into UK - ADMS.	£390 + VAT
Data For Almanac Dispersion Model	Frequency Analysis of wind speed and direction and total cloud amount as a function of seasons.	£240 + VAT
Wind Frequency Analysis	Numeric representation of wind speed for 30 degree sectors for a 10 year period. Month and Annual Analysis Annual Analysis	£180 + VAT £120 + VAT
Wind Rose Analysis	Pictorial representation of wind speed for 30 degree sectors for a 10 year period. Month, Seasonal and Annual Analysis Annual Analysis	£120 + VAT £ 60 + VAT
Wasp Analysis	Pictorial and Numeric representation of wind speed for 30 degree sectors. Data for a NGR location can be estimated using the nearest representative Meteorological site.	£380 + VAT
Inversion Frequency Analysis	Number of Inversions as a function of Layers above the surface. Inversions within these layers being described in terms of thicknesses and temperature differences. Analysis in terms of total number of Inversions, mean annual and mean seasonal values. Analysis is run over a 1 year period.	£250 + VAT

AIR POLLUTION RELATED PACKAGES

Current Price List (3) April 1994

Product	Brief Description	Price
Upper Air Data	An Upper Air Ascent giving temperature, dew point, relative humidity, wind speed and direction at given pressure / height levels. (for 00 GMT or 12 GMT). An additional charge is made for staff time and consumables.	£12.50 + VAT per ascent

Most Analysis are run over a 10 year period depending on the availability of data.

For further information please contact

Pauline Tonkinson (0344) 856971
Heather Stevens (0344) 856965

FAX (0344) 854588

Environmental Consultancy Services (Air Pollution)
Meteorological Office Commercial Services
Room JG9 Johnson House
London Road
Bracknell
Berkshire
RG12 2SY

METEOROLOGICAL DATA SOFTWARE

Packages - April 1994

The Meteorological Office is able to provide data sets of weather elements plus calculated values of Boundary Layer Depth and Paquill Stability Category for input into Pollution Dispersion Software. The data is quality controlled and can be either hourly or three hourly as required.

The cost for this type of data is dependent upon the number of elements requested. There is a weighting factor which decreases as the volume of data supplied increases, and the charges for this form of data are currently as follows:-

Hourly Data, 24 observations per day

	3 Met Elements & BLD & PSC	4 Met Elements & BLD & PSC	5 Met Elements & BLD & PSC
1 days data	£ 5+VAT	£ 7+VAT	£ 9+VAT
1 months data	£ 167 +VAT	£ 223 +VAT	£ 280 +VAT
1 years data	£ 1525 +VAT	£ 1855 +VAT	£ 2147 +VAT
5 years data	£ 3905 +VAT	£ 4366 +VAT	£ 4812 +VAT

3 - Hourly Data, 8 observations per day

	3 Met Elements & BLD & PSC	4 Met Elements & BLD & PSC	5 Met Elements & BLD & PSC
1 days data	£ 2+VAT	£ 2+VAT	£ 3+VAT
1 months data	£ 56 +VAT	£ 75 +VAT	£ 93 +VAT
1 years data	£ 657 +VAT	£ 844 +VAT	£ 998 +VAT
5 years data	£ 2148 +VAT	£ 2570 +VAT	£ 2924 +VAT

These are standard charges for all customers, and take into account the cost of collecting, quality controlling and archiving the data. An additional charge is made for staff time and consumables.

All data supplied is subject to Crown Copyright, and a copy of the restricted use agreement form, 'Conditions for the supply of Meteorological Data', is enclosed for perusal.

This is an Agreement ("the Agreement") between The Met. Office, London Road, Bracknell, Berkshire RG12 2SZ ("The Met. Office") and

.....
.....
.....
.....
..... ("the Client")

whereby The Met. Office undertakes to provide the following Service

.....
.....
.....
.....
..... ("the Service")
for the period

under the following payments terms

.....
..... ("the Price")

and under the Standard Terms and Conditions which are attached to this document and which form part of the Agreement.

Signed.....on behalf of The Met. Office
on.....(date)

Signed.....on behalf of the Client
on.....(date)

Terms and Conditions

1. The Met. Office will use all reasonable endeavours to provide the Service as specified in this Agreement but will not be liable if prevented from doing so by circumstances beyond its control.
2. The Client will pay the Price including any V.A.T. or other duties or taxes as specified in this Agreement and make payments within 30 calendar days of the date of any invoice for the Service. The Met. Office reserves the right to levy a charge for costs incurred because of late payment.
3. The Met. Office will not be liable to the Client for loss or damage suffered by the Client unless due to the negligence of the Met. Office in performing its obligations under this Agreement save where either condition 4 or 5 applies. The Client undertakes with the Met. Office to keep the Met. Office fully and effectually indemnified against all claims demands losses expenses and costs which the Met. Office may incur as a result of any breach by the Client of any provision contained in this Agreement.
4. Where the Client uses equipment not supplied by the Met. Office for the receipt of all or any part of the Service the Met. Office will not be liable for any damage loss or injury arising from any fault in such equipment or failure to receive the Service or any part of it by such equipment.
5. All information data tables chart reports or advice in whatever form specified as part of the Service and connected with the provision of the Service will be referred to hereinafter as Information. Whilst all reasonable efforts will be made to provide accurate and reliable Information the Met. Office will not be liable for any damage loss or injury arising from loss of information or errors in the Information.
6. The Client will not pass on sell all or any part of the Information to any third party including any associated company of the Client without prior consent from the Met. Office.
7. The Client acknowledges that copyright in the information is vested in the crown ("Crown Copyright") and will ensure that such copyright is acknowledged in any reproduction of the Information in a manner specified by the Met. Office. The Client will not cause or permit anything to be done which may damage or infringe Crown Copyright or other intellectual property rights in the Information of the Crown's title to the Information or assist or allow others to do so.
8. The Client will promptly notify the Met. Office of any development or enhancement of the Service of Information which the Client makes in the course of its use or any innovation relating thereto and any such development enhancement or innovation may be used freely by the Met. Office and its licensees without any payment being made in respect thereof by the Met. Office.
9. The Client undertakes to comply with the terms of any notice specifying a breach of the provisions of this Agreement and with such steps as are reasonably required by the Met. Office to remedy such breach but nothing in this clause is intended to require the Met. Office to serve notice of any breach before taking action in respect of it.
10. The Met. Office will be entitled without prejudice to any other rights or remedies it may have to terminate this Agreement immediately if:
 - a. The Client fails to make punctual payment of any sums due to the Met. Office under the terms of the Agreement or
 - b. The Client fails to observe any obligation under this Agreement or
 - c. The Client becomes insolvent or makes any composition or arrangement with creditors or goes into liquidation (other than a member's voluntary liquidation) or has a receiver (including an Administrative Receiver) appointed over the whole or any part of the Client's assets or
 - d. Crown Copyright in the information or any other intellectual property rights of the Crown in the Information are infringed prejudiced or put in jeopardy.
11. In the event of this Agreement being determined whether by effluxion of time breach or otherwise the Client will immediately pay to the Met. Office all arrears of Payments and all further sums which would but for the determination of this Agreement have fallen due at the end of the Term of this Agreement.
12. The Client warrants that it has the power to enter into this Agreement and has all necessary approvals to do so.
13. The receipt of money by the Met. Office will not prevent the Met. Office from questioning the Correctness of any statement in respect of such monies.
14. The Client will make no statements representations or claims and will give no warranties to any of its Clients or prospective Clients in respect of the Information or the Service save such as are implied by law or may have been specifically authorised by the Met. Office.
15. If any terms or provision or any part thereof (in this clause called "the Offending Provision") contained in this Agreement shall be declared or become unenforceable invalid or illegal for any reason the other terms and provisions or other part thereof contained in this Agreement will remain in full force and effect as if the Agreement had been executed without the Offending Provision appearing herein, unless the Offending Provision affects The Met. Office's right to receive payment or supply the Services or adversely affects Crown Copyright or any other intellectual property rights in the Information in which case the Met. Office may terminate this Agreement upon 30 days written notice.
16. Each of the parties will give notice to the other of the change or acquisition of any address or telephone, facsimile, telex or similar number relevant to this Agreement at the earliest possible opportunity.
17. Any notice to be served on either of the parties by the other will be sent by prepaid recorded delivery registered post or by telex or electronic mail or by facsimile transmission and will be deemed to have been received by the addressee within 72 hours of posting or if sent back by telex or electronic mail to the correct telex number (correct answerback) or correct electronic mail number or facsimile transmission number of the addressee within 24 hours of transmission unless previously acknowledged by the addressee.
18. The client will not assign any of its rights under this Agreement without prior consent in writing of the Met. Office.
19. The Agreement will be governed by English Law in every particular including formation and interpretation and will be deemed to have been made in England and the English Courts will have exclusive jurisdiction.
20. The failure of either party to enforce at any time or for any period any one or more of the terms or conditions of this Agreement will not be a waiver of them or of the right at any time subsequently to enforce all terms and conditions of this Agreement.
21. The Client acknowledges that this Agreement and the Standard Terms and Conditions relating to it contain the whole Agreement between the parties and that it has not relied upon any oral or written representation made to it by the Met. Office or its employees or agents and has made its own independent investigations into all matters relevant to this Agreement.

METEOROLOGICAL DATA SETS SUITABLE FOR POLLUTION DISPERSION MODELS

Two sets of data are provided :-

- 1) Table 1. Hourly surface meteorological data.
- 2) Table 2. Twice daily mixing layer depth (morning and afternoon).

DATA FORMAT (1993 VERSION)

Table 1	Columns	Format	Description
	1 - 5	I5	WMO Station Number (Surface)
	6 - 7	I2	Year (last 2 digits)
	8 - 9	I2	Month
	10 - 11	I2	Day
	12 - 13	I2	Hour (GMT)
	14 - 16	3A1	Ceiling Height (hundreds of feet) This refers to the base of the lowest cloud layer covering at least 6 / 10 of the sky
	17 - 38	not read	
	39 - 40	I2	Wind Direction (tens of degrees from true North). Direction from which the wind is blowing
	41 - 42	I2	Wind Speed (Knots)
	43 - 46	not read	
	47 - 49	I3	Dry Bulb Temperature (degrees Fahrenheit)
	50 - 55	not read	
	56	A1	Total Sky Cover (tenths)
	57 - 78	not read	
	79	A1	Total Opaque Sky Cover (tenths)
Table 2	Columns	Format	Description
	1 - 5	I5	WMO Station Number (Surface)
	6 - 7	I2	Year (last 2 digits)
	8 - 9	I2	Month
	10 - 11	I2	Day
	12 - 13	not read	
	14 - 17	I4	Morning Mixing Height (metres) (Calculated from Surface Observation)
	18 - 31	not read	
	32 - 35	I4	Afternoon Mixing Height (metres) (Calculated from Surface Observations)

N.B.

Temperature is converted from Degrees Celsius to Degrees Fahrenheit. Cloud Amount is converted from eighths to tenths, and is encoded as 0 to 9 for 0/10ths to 9/10ths of cloud and as '-' for 10/10ths of cloud. Sky obscured is coded as '000' height and '-' for 10/10ths of cloud. No cloud is coded as '---' height and 0/10ths cloud amount. For cloud amounts less than 6/10ths the Ceiling Height is coded as '---'.
Conditions can occur when there is 6/10ths or more total cloud amount but no individual layer covers 6/10ths or more of the sky.

METEOROLOGICAL DATA SETS SUITABLE FOR POLLUTION DISPERSION MODELS

Two sets of data are provided :-

- 1) Table 1. Hourly surface meteorological data.
- 2) Table 2. Twice daily mixing layer depth (morning and afternoon).

DATA FORMAT

Table	Columns	Format	Description
Table 1	1 - 5	I5	WMO Station Number (Surface)
	6 - 7	I2	Year (last 2 digits)
	8 - 9	I2	Month
	10 - 11	I2	Day
	12 - 13	I2	Hour (GMT)
	14 - 16	3A1	Ceiling Height (hundreds of feet) This refers to the base of the lowest cloud layer covering at least 6 / 10 of the sky
	17 - 38	not read	Wind Direction (tens of degrees from true North). Direction from which the wind is blowing
	39 - 40	I2	
	41 - 42	I2	Wind Speed (Knots)
	43 - 46	not read	Dry Bulb Temperature (degrees Fahrenheit)
	47 - 49	I3	
	50 - 55	not read	Total Sky Cover (tenths)
	56	A1	
	57 - 78	not read	Total Opaque Sky Cover (tenths)
79	A1		
Table 2	1 - 5	I5	WMO Station Number (Surface)
	6 - 7	I2	Year (last 2 digits)
	8 - 9	I2	Month
	10	not read	Day
	11 - 12	I2	
	13	not read	Morning Mixing Height (metres) (Calculated from Surface Observation)
	14 - 17	I4	
	18 - 24	not read	Afternoon Mixing Height (metres) (Calculated from Surface Observations)
	25 - 28	I4	

N.B.
Temperature is converted from Degrees Celsius to Degrees Fahrenheit. Cloud Amount is converted from eights to tenths, and is encoded as 0 to 9 for 0/10ths to 9/10ths of cloud and as '-' for 10/10ths of cloud. Sky obscured is coded as '000' height and '-' for 10/10ths of cloud. No cloud is coded as '---' height and 0/10ths cloud amount. For cloud amounts less than 6/10ths the Ceiling Height is coded as '---'. Conditions can occur when there is 6/10ths or more total cloud amount but no individual layer covers 6/10ths or more of the sky.

METEOROLOGICAL DATA SETS SUITABLE FOR POLLUTION DISPERSION MODELS

The analysis calculates both rural and urban mixing heights.

DATA FORMAT

First Line

Columns	Format	Description
1 - 5	I5	WMO Station Number (Surface)
6	not read	
7 - 8	I2	Year (last 2 digits)
9	not read	
10 - 14	I5	WMO Station Number (Surface)
15	not read	
16 - 17	I2	Year (last 2 digits)

Remainder of the dataset

Columns	Format	Description
1 - 2	I2	Year (last 2 digits)
3 - 4	I2	Month
5 - 6	I2	Day
7 - 8	I2	Hour (GMT) (01 to 24)
9 - 17	F9.4	Flow Vector (tens of degrees from true North). Direction towards which the wind is blowing.
18 - 26	F9.4	Wind Speed (metres per second)
27 - 32	F6.1	Ambient Temperature (Kelvin)
33 - 34	I2	Stability Class There are 6 categories used to define Stability from A (very unstable) through D (neutral) to F (very stable)
35 - 41	F7.1	Rural Mixing Height (metres) (Calculated from Surface Observation)
42 - 48	F7.1	Urban Mixing Height (metres) (Calculated from Surface Observations)

N.B.

Temperature is converted from Degrees Celsius to Degrees Kelvin.
Wind Speed is converted from knots to metres per second.

Climatological Data Bank Stations providing hourly SYNOPTIC observations and daily CLIMATE messages

- KEY:**
- STATION NAME** ■ M.O Key Stations
7 days a week/24 hr coverage
 - Station name ■ M.O 7 days a week/24 hr coverage
 - M.O Incomplete programme
 - M.O Rooftop sites
 - Auxiliary 24 hr coverage
hourly or 3 hourly
 - Auxiliary, mainly daytime
 - Auxiliary, minor
 - ▲ SAWS installed
 - △ SAWS planned

FULL RANGE OF HOURLY PARAMETERS ARE:-

1	DY	DAY OF MONTH	
2	HR		GMT
3	IB	WMO BLOCK NUMBER	
4	II	WMO STATION NUMBER	
5	YR	YEAR	
6	MN	MONTH	
7	DD	WIND DIRECTION	0 TRUE
8	FF	WIND SPEED	KNOTS
9	WW	PRESENT WEATHER	WW CODE
10	W	PAST WEATHER	W CODE
11	N	TOTAL CLOUD AMOUNT	OKTAS
12	CL	LOW CLOUD TYPE	CL CODE
13	CM	MEDIUM CLOUD TYPE	CM CODE
14	CH	HIGH CLOUD TYPE	CH CODE
15	NL	TOTAL LOW CLOUD AMOUNT	OKTAS
16	HT	BASE OF LOWEST CLOUD	DAM
17	VV	VISIBILITY	DAM
18	TT	DRY BULB TEMPERATURE	0.1°C
19	TW	WET BULB TEMPERATURE	0.1°C
20	TD	DEW POINT TEMPERATURE	0.1°C
21	VP	VAPOUR PRESSURE	0.1 MB
22	RH	RELATIVE HUMIDITY	%
23	PP	MSL PRESSURE	0.1 MB
24	GR	GLOBAL RADIATION	W / M ²
25	SS	HOURLY SUNSHINE	0.1 HR
26	E	STATE OF GROUND	E CODE
27	RR	HOURLY RAINFALL AMOUNT	0.1 MM
28	RD	HOURLY RAINFALL DURATION	MINUTES
29	MD	MEAN HOURLY WIND DIRECTION	DEGREES TRUE
30	MS	MEAN HOURLY WIND SPEED	KNOTS
31			
32			
33	NS	SIG CLOUD AMOUNT	OKTAS
34	CS	SIG CLOUD TYPE	C CODE
35	HS	SIG CLOUD BASE	DAM
36	NS	SIG CLOUD AMOUNT	OKTAS
37	CS	SIG CLOUD TYPE	C CODE
38	HS	SIG CLOUD BASE	DAM
39	NS	SIG CLOUD AMOUNT	OKTAS
40	CS	SIG CLOUD TYPE	C CODE
41	HS	SIG CLOUD BASE	DAM
42	VE	VERTICAL VISIBILITY	DAM
43			
44	GD	MAX HOURLY GUST DIRECTION	0 TRUE
45	GS	MAX HOURLY GUST SPEED	KNOTS
46	GT	MAX HOURLY GUST TIME	MINS
47			
48			
49			
50			

PRODUCED BY ADVISORY SERVICES METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE BRACKNELL ON 25. 9. 1991 KNOWN COPYRIGHT
 HOURLY DATA FOR STATION AUGHTON AUGUST 1991

Thur 1					Fri 2					Sat 3					Sun 4				
HR	DD	FF	RH	PP	DD	FF	RH	PP	DD	FF	RH	PP	DD	FF	RH	PP			
0	240	2	82	1009.5	230	2	93	1017.5	50	5	76	1021.0	200	5	80	1022.6			
1	210	2	83	1009.4	210	2	91	1017.5	100	4	79	1020.8	200	4	80	1022.7			
2	120	3	83	1009.4	260	2	90	1017.7	120	4	81	1020.5	170	3	82	1022.6			
3	130	3	82	1009.8	260	4	88	1017.8	130	3	88	1020.2	130	6	89	1022.7			
4	140	5	87	1010.0	260	3	90	1017.9	130	6	89	1020.3	120	5	92	1022.9			
5	140	3	89	1010.2	0	0	90	1018.1	120	5	91	1020.2	100	6	91	1023.0			
6	140	5	88	1010.5	130	2	93	1018.5	130	6	92	1020.4	110	5	91	1023.0			
7	130	5	85	1010.8	120	2	85	1018.8	140	5	86	1020.7	120	4	84	1023.2			
8	160	6	73	1011.3	180	2	80	1019.3	160	7	77	1020.9	150	6	83	1023.3			
9	160	7	69	1011.8	0	0	79	1019.3	160	2	71	1020.7	140	6	80	1023.3			
10	200	7	64	1012.0	320	2	79	1019.7	180	6	76	1020.9	180	4	71	1022.9			
11	210	9	61	1012.4	210	2	72	1020.0	170	7	77	1020.9	260	6	64	1022.8			
12	220	6	62	1012.6	240	2	67	1020.3	150	7	74	1020.7	240	7	64	1022.5			
13	240	4	75	1013.2	310	3	66	1020.3	170	8	76	1020.6	270	5	67	1022.5			
14	250	5	72	1013.5	290	7	68	1020.5	250	7	72	1020.3	290	5	61	1022.2			
15	240	10	63	1013.6	300	6	74	1020.9	250	10	68	1020.5	290	7	62	1021.7			
16	240	7	66	1014.1	260	6	60	1020.6	250	11	70	1020.6	290	7	64	1021.1			
17	250	7	71	1014.7	310	5	63	1020.6	260	10	65	1020.9	280	7	61	1020.7			
18	250	6	74	1015.1	320	6	65	1020.7	270	10	70	1021.2	330	2	65	1020.1			
19	280	3	80	1015.4	320	3	70	1021.0	260	5	72	1021.9	340	2	67	1019.6			
20	270	3	82	1015.8	20	2	79	1021.0	230	6	71	1022.1	330	2	76	1019.4			
21	280	4	89	1016.6	30	4	78	1021.2	220	6	77	1022.4	0	0	82	1019.1			
22	0	0	89	1016.9	50	6	72	1020.9	200	5	78	1022.5	0	0	84	1018.8			
23	210	3	83	1017.4	50	5	73	1020.9	190	3	82	1022.4	180	6	87	1018.7			

Mon 5					Tues 6					Wed 7					Thur 8				
HR	DD	FF	RH	PP	DD	FF	RH	PP	DD	FF	RH	PP	DD	FF	RH	PP			
0	170	7	82	1018.0	160	2	97	1010.5	310	10	94	1010.6	320	6	89	1018.4			
1	190	6	76	1017.5	180	2	98	1009.8	340	6	92	1011.4	330	5	91	1018.7			
2	180	7	83	1017.3	160	6	97	1009.3	320	4	93	1012.1	330	7	91	1019.0			
3	170	6	90	1016.7	160	5	99	1008.9	320	3	91	1012.3	340	4	92	1019.2			
4	160	7	88	1015.9	150	3	99	1008.2	340	2	95	1012.4	330	7	89	1019.7			
5	150	8	84	1015.4	130	4	100	1007.5	350	5	94	1012.6	350	4	97	1020.5			
6	150	9	84	1014.8	120	6	100	1006.6	350	2	92	1013.0	330	6	96	1020.8			
7	160	6	84	1014.7	130	7	99	1006.1	10	4	88	1013.6	310	12	83	1021.3			
8	150	10	82	1014.2	150	8	98	1005.9	30	4	77	1014.0	320	7	81	1022.0			
9	150	8	89	1014.0	170	10	95	1005.6	10	2	71	1014.5	310	10	72	1022.6			
10	170	10	80	1013.3	200	11	79	1005.4	40	4	67	1014.7	310	10	73	1023.2			
11	180	10	81	1013.4	210	10	81	1005.6	10	3	63	1014.7	300	10	71	1023.5			
12	180	7	82	1013.3	250	7	84	1005.7	310	7	77	1015.0	290	8	64	1023.7			
13	220	12	76	1013.4	240	10	88	1005.9	320	8	84	1015.4	280	8	73	1024.1			
14	250	9	84	1013.7	250	8	88	1006.1	310	8	84	1015.6	270	9	65	1024.3			
15	240	7	88	1013.7	260	10	97	1006.4	330	7	82	1015.6	290	7	58	1024.6			
16	250	4	91	1013.0	270	10	93	1006.5	300	8	80	1015.6	280	9	53	1024.8			
17	190	4	95	1013.0	300	11	95	1007.4	310	8	79	1016.0	280	6	59	1025.0			
18	240	4	94	1012.5	300	11	94	1008.2	310	7	77	1016.4	260	8	56	1024.8			
19	200	2	97	1012.4	290	11	91	1009.0	310	6	79	1016.6	260	5	60	1024.8			
20	200	4	90	1012.0	290	10	89	1009.7	300	6	83	1017.2	300	2	69	1024.7			
21	180	5	93	1011.8	300	9	92	1009.9	300	5	87	1017.5	200	2	73	1025.3			
22	180	4	94	1011.5	270	7	93	1011.5	290	4	92	1017.7	200	2	78	1025.2			
23	170	4	94	1011.1	310	8	93	1010.9	310	6	91	1017.9	200	3	76	1025.1			

EXAMPLE OF HOURLY DATA WHICH CAN BE SUPPLIED ON PAPER OR DISK.

STATION NUMBER DCNN	YEAR	MONTH	DAY	HOUR GMT	WIND SPEED KNOTS	WIND DIRECTION DEGREES TRUE	AMBIENT AIR TEMPERATURE DEGREES CENTIGRADE	AIR PRESSURE MBS	ATMOSPHERIC PRESSURE MBS	BOUNDARY LAYER DEPTH METRES	PASQUILL STABILITY CODE
5113	1991	5	25	00	3	30	12.0	1030.0	1030.0	29	9
5113	1991	5	25	01	0	0	11.5	1029.0	1029.0	20	9
5113	1991	5	25	02	2	320	11.1	1029.8	1029.8	9	9
5113	1991	5	25	03	0	0	10.7	1029.6	1029.6	9	9
5113	1991	5	25	04	0	0	10.4	1029.6	1029.6	22	9
5113	1991	5	25	05	0	0	10.7	1029.5	1029.5	81	9
5113	1991	5	25	06	0	0	11.6	1029.5	1029.5	196	3
5113	1991	5	25	07	2	270	12.2	1029.7	1029.7	391	3
5113	1991	5	25	08	5	260	13.7	1030.2	1030.2	643	3
5113	1991	5	25	09	5	290	14.8	1029.8	1029.8	863	3
5113	1991	5	25	10	4	230	15.6	1029.5	1029.5	1084	3
5113	1991	5	25	12	6	290	16.8	1029.4	1029.4	1145	4
5113	1991	5	25	13	7	290	17.4	1029.4	1029.4	1212	4
5113	1991	5	25	14	7	280	18.9	1029.3	1029.3	1312	4
5113	1991	5	25	15	9	10	20.2	1029.1	1029.1	1390	6
5113	1991	5	25	16	10	310	19.1	1028.7	1028.7	1426	7
5113	1991	5	25	17	11	340	18.5	1028.7	1028.7	1464	7
5113	1991	5	25	18	10	330	17.5	1028.8	1028.8	1475	5
5113	1991	5	25	19	9	320	16.3	1028.9	1028.9	1456	7
5113	1991	5	25	20	8	340	14.5	1029.3	1029.3	679	7
5113	1991	5	25	21	6	330	13.4	1030.2	1030.2	512	7
5113	1991	5	25	22	6	330	12.2	1030.4	1030.4	512	8
5113	1991	5	25	23	4	320	11.7	1030.3	1030.3	300	7

CLIMATOLOGICAL SUMMARY

EXPLANATION OF OUTPUT

Using data from the Meteorological Office 'MAD' series of archived daily climatological data, this program evaluates averages and extremes at a specified station over a specified period for a wide range of meteorological elements. The data are checked for rogue values using quality-control routines which are built-in or user-specified.

The monthly summary provides a convenient reference summary over the averaging period. The table is divided into five sections - Temperature, Precipitation, Sunshine, Wind Speed, and 'Number of days with' parameters. The values presented, in the order in which they appear across the page, are as follows:-

Temperature:	Mean daily maximum, mean daily minimum; Highest daily maximum and date of occurrence; Lowest daily minimum and date; No. of air frost (screen min < 0.0 deg C). ** Note : For all UK stations max and min terminal hours are 0900 GMT (not 0900 - 2100 / 2100 - 0900). Overseas stations are usually morning - morning.
Precipitation:	Total ppt amount; Total ppt duration; Highest daily ppt total, and date; No. of 'rain days' (ppt 0.2 mm or more within 'rainfall - day', 0900 to 0900 GMT); No. of 'wet days' (0.1 mm or more during 'rainfall day').
Sunshine:	Total hours of sunshine; sunniest day and date; No. of days with nil sunshine recorded, and no. of days with nine hours or more.
Wind Speed:	Monthly mean speed (mean of daily (24H) mean speed for month); Highest 24H mean speed (0000 - 2400 H for tabulated anemograph data, 0900 - 0900 GMT for 'run of wind' records) and date ; Highest gust during month, and date ; and No. of days (0000 - 2400 H) with gusts of 34 kts or more, and 48 kts or more
No. of days with	SF - Snow or sleet observed to fall at any time during the civil day (midnight to midnight). SL - Snow lying (covering > 50% of area representative of the station) at the morning observation - usually 0900 GMT in UK. HL - Hail (pieces of ice of diameter 5 mm or more) observed to fall at any time during the civil day. TH - Thunder heard at any time during the civil day. GA - Gale (mean wind speed 34 kts or more for at least 10 minutes) at any time during the civil day. FG - Fog (visiblity < 1000 m) - at 0900 H observation in UK (but at any time for overseas stations).

The annual Summary presents total or mean (as appropriate) of each of the elements above, including date and time of month of the highest daily maximum, the lowest daily minimum, and the highest daily rainfall amount. Additionally, the mean annual temperature (derived from (mean annual maximum and minimum) / 2) is printed underneath and between the mean annual max. and min.

STATION NUMBER
WMO STN. NO.

STATION NAME -

CLIMATOLOGICAL MEANS & EXTREMES

LATITUDE
LONGITUDE
N.G. REF.
ALTITUDE

PERIOD OF AVERAGES:
PERIOD OF EXTREMES:

EXAMPLE SECTION 1

CLIMATOLOGICAL MEANS AND EXTREMES - PART 1

	NO. OF												ANNUAL	YEARS
	JAN	FEB	MCH	APL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUG	SEPT	OCT	NOV	DEC		
TEMPERATURE - DEGREES C														
ABSOLUTE MAXIMUM	13.3	16.6	20.4	22.7	26.7	27.1	31.8	33.2	27.0	25.4	16.5	14.3	33.2	10
AVERAGE MONTHLY MAXIMUM	11.5	12.0	15.3	18.5	22.0	24.8	27.6	27.9	24.4	20.6	14.9	13.0	29.0*1	10
MEAN DAILY MAXIMUM	6.1	5.6	9.3	11.8	15.5	18.2	21.6	21.7	18.4	14.4	9.3	7.5	13.4	10
MEAN DAILY MINIMUM	0.3	0.0	1.9	3.3	6.5	9.3	11.9	11.6	9.7	7.6	3.5	2.2	5.7	10
AVERAGE MONTHLY MINIMUM	-6.1	-5.6	-3.2	-2.3	0.7	4.0	7.0	6.4	3.8	0.4	-3.0	-3.9	-7.9*2	10
ABSOLUTE MINIMUM	-14.2	-9.6	-6.6	-4.1	-0.4	0.5	5.8	4.6	1.6	-3.5	-6.2	-8.5	-14.2	10
HIGHEST MINIMUM	11.0	9.6	11.0	11.2	13.6	16.8	18.1	17.9	16.0	15.3	12.4	10.8	18.1	10
LOWEST MAXIMUM	-6.5	-4.1	-1.4	3.9	7.2	11.3	14.2	12.5	11.2	7.8	0.5	-1.6	-6.5	10
PRECIPITATION - MILLIMETRES														
MONTHLY AVERAGE AMOUNT	55	34	44	43	45	61	44	43	45	68	53	50	585	10
WETTEST MONTH ON RECORD	132.8	69.0	79.3	94.1	72.8	113.8	101.2	105.1	104.8	120.2	73.6	96.9	717.8	10
DRIEST MONTH ON RECORD	22.6	10.7	13.5	8.8	5.1	16.3	11.7	13.0	6.8	11.2	25.8	20.1	477.6	10
MAXIMUM FALL IN 24 HRS	20.8	22.0	18.2	23.9	32.8	17.5	29.1	35.0	31.5	33.6	26.8	29.8	35.0	10
SUNSHINE - HOURS														
MONTHLY AVERAGE	67	84	114	171	212	191	222	213	149	115	72	52	1662	10
SUNNIEST MONTH ON RECORD	92.1	127.0	163.7	254.2	331.0	268.4	279.3	279.9	194.6	138.0	114.1	74.0	1998.1	10
DULLEST MONTH ON RECORD	46.7	42.0	57.2	123.3	136.8	136.5	167.8	160.5	102.6	77.9	41.4	26.7	1415.9	10
SUNNIEST DAY ON RECORD	8.4	9.5	10.9	13.6	15.3	15.6	15.4	13.7	12.0	9.8	8.6	7.0	15.6	10
NO. OF DAYS WITH-														
NIL SUNSHINE	11.5	7.8	4.9	2.6	2.5	1.5	0.9	1.0	2.8	4.9	9.0	12.5	61.9	10
9HR OR MORE SUNSHINE	0.0	0.7	2.0	7.9	12.0	9.1	11.4	10.2	4.5	1.5	0.0	0.0	59.3	10
WIND SPEED - KNOTS														
MEAN SPEED	11.1	10.6	10.5	9.4	8.6	8.2	7.8	8.3	8.6	9.3	9.2	10.0	9.3	9
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	26.5	28.5	26.8	23.0	18.2	16.6	15.3	16.1	21.6	23.0	21.1	23.0	28.5	9
AVG. MONTHLY GUST	53	47	49	40	36	35	34	34	41	46	44	49	60*1	9
HIGHEST GUST ON RECORD	80	71	63	49	43	40	39	40	46	72	60	58	80	9

*1 - AVERAGE OF THE HIGHEST VALUE(S) IN EVERY YEAR

*2 - AVERAGE OF THE LOWEST VALUE(S) IN EVERY YEAR

DATES OF EXTREMES ARE GIVEN IN PARTS 3 & 4

PERIOD: 1/1/1983 TO 31/12/1989
 MONTHS AND HOURS USED: ALL

MONTH 1 JAN

FREQUENCY TABLE

HOUR (GMT)	PASQUILL STABILITY CATEGORY										TOTAL
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
22 TO 0	0	0	0	0	0	0	521	61	64	5	651
1 TO 3	0	0	0	0	0	0	521	73	54	3	651
4 TO 6	0	0	0	0	0	0	536	56	56	3	651
7 TO 9	0	0	8	0	34	0	548	33	26	2	651
10 TO 12	0	0	47	0	207	0	397	0	0	0	651
13 TO 15	0	0	21	0	169	0	461	0	0	0	651
16 TO 18	0	0	0	0	0	0	533	57	61	0	651
19 TO 21	0	0	0	0	0	0	503	83	61	4	651
TOTALS	0	0	76	0	410	0	4020	363	322	17	5208

PERCENTAGE FREQUENCY TABLE BY ROW

HOUR (GMT)	PASQUILL STABILITY CATEGORY										TOTAL
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
22 TO 0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	80.0	9.4	9.8	0.8	100.0
1 TO 3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	80.0	11.2	8.3	0.5	100.0
4 TO 6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	82.3	8.6	8.6	0.5	100.0
7 TO 9	0.0	0.0	1.2	0.0	5.2	0.0	84.2	5.1	4.0	0.3	100.0
10 TO 12	0.0	0.0	7.2	0.0	31.8	0.0	61.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0
13 TO 15	0.0	0.0	3.2	0.0	26.0	0.0	70.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0
16 TO 18	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	81.9	8.8	9.4	0.0	100.0
19 TO 21	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	77.3	12.7	9.4	0.6	100.0
TOTALS	0.0	0.0	1.5	0.0	7.9	0.0	77.2	7.0	6.2	0.3	100.0

CLIMATOLOGICAL MEANS & EXTREMES

EXAMPLE SECTION 2

STATION NUMBER -
WMO STN. NO

PERIOD OF AVERAGES:

LATITUDE
LONGITUDE
N/G REF
ALTITUDE

CLIMATOLOGICAL MEANS AND EXTREMES - PART 2

	JAN	FEB	MCH	APL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUG	SEPT	OCT	NOV	DEC	ANNUAL YEARS
NO OF DAYS WITH:													
AIR FROST (MIN <0C)	126	130	76	42	03	00	00	00	00	01	57	77	51.2 10
GROUND FROST (G MIN <0C)	190	182	180	12.3	49	12	00	00	22	39	11.2	14.4	105.3 10
*SNOW/SLEET FALLING	68	79	46	23	00	00	00	00	00	00	1.1	19	246 10
SNOW LYING AT 09H GMT	49	57	06	01	00	00	00	00	00	00	07	04	124 10
*THUNDER HEARD	01	02	06	10	30	36	29	19	13	09	01	01	157 10
*HAIL (>5MM DIAM)	01	01	11	02	05	03	00	00	00	01	00	00	24 10
*ICE PELLETS (<5MM DIAM)	20	34	22	21	08	02	03	00	05	03	04	04	126 10
FOG AT 09H GMT	19	23	16	03	02	01	02	02	08	11	26	33	146 10
*GALE (34KN FOR 10 MIN)	09	09	05	01	00	00	00	00	00	02	04	02	32 10
*GUSTS OF 34KN OR MORE	70	53	54	32	14	09	10	11	28	40	37	54	412 9
*GUSTS OF 48KN OR MORE	11	15	09	02	00	00	00	00	00	01	03	07	48 9
PRECIP. 0.2MM OR MORE	178	120	161	138	128	150	104	98	120	136	154	145	1632 10
PRECIP. 1.0MM OR MORE	119	84	11.3	96	84	113	77	68	81	92	101	96	1124 10
PRECIP. 10 MM OR MORE	08	03	04	07	11	21	13	11	09	18	13	10	128 10
PRECIP. 25 MM OR MORE	00	00	00	00	01	00	01	01	01	04	02	01	11 10

* - AT ANY TIME DURING THE CIVIL DAY, MIDNIGHT TO MIDNIGHT

PASQUILL STABILITY FREQUENCY ANALYSIS

The Pasquill Stability Categories were defined to describe the stability of the lowest layers of the atmosphere so that they could be used for estimating the dispersion of air pollution released from the ground or from industrial stacks.

There are 7 categories from A (very unstable) through D (neutral) to G (very stable). In addition hybrid categories A/B, B/C and C/D which are intermediate between A and B, B and C, C and D were also defined.

Category A (Very Unstable) occurs typically on a warm sunny summer afternoon with light winds and almost cloudless skies when there is strong solar heating of the ground and the air immediately above the surface. Bubbles of warm air rise from the ground in thermals. The lapse rate near the surface is super - adiabatic (i.e. it exceeds the dry adiabatic lapse rate).

Category D (Neutral) occurs in cloudy conditions or whenever there is a strong surface wind to cause vigorous mechanical mixing of the lower atmosphere. This category occurs both day and night. The period immediately after sunrise and immediately before sunset is normally considered neutral. The lapse rate is equal to or less than the dry adiabatic lapse rate.

Category G (Very Stable) occurs typically on a cold clear calm night when there is strong cooling of the ground and the lowest layers of the atmosphere by long wave radiation to space. There is a strong inversion of temperature. Category G only occurs at night.

Categories E and F also only occur at night normally with a slight or moderate inversion of temperature.

The Stability Categories are estimated from the total cloud amount, wind speed and time of year.

During the day an estimate is made of the incident solar radiation and this is combined with the wind speed to estimate the Stability Category.

At night the Stability Category is a simple function of cloud cover and wind speed.

Section 1 of the Stability Frequency Analysis gives the frequency distribution of the Stability Categories as a function of time of day for each month and for the whole year.

Section 2 gives the frequency distribution of the Stability Categories by time of day and month for each Stability Category.

Section 3 gives the frequency distribution of the Stability Categories as a function of wind direction and wind speed for each month and the whole year.

The wind speed classes are 0, 1-3, 4-6, 7-10, 11-16, 17-98 knots (corresponding to the Beaufort Forces 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 or greater). The wind direction is the direction from which the wind blows, and can be classified in either twelve 30 degree direction sectors and calm or sixteen 22.5 degrees direction sectors agreeing with the 16 cardinal points of the Compass and calm.

Originally the wind direction was observed to the nearest 10 degrees from True North so that the sector labelled 341-010 degrees (for example) actually contains the observations originally recorded as 350, 360 and 010 degrees.

MODIFIED PASQUILL STABILITY CATEGORIES

Wind Speed (Knots)	Day-time (excluding Dawn and Dusk) from 1 hour After Sunrise till 1 hour Before Sunset				Dawn and Dusk	Night-time Total Cloud Amount (Oktas)		
	Incoming solar radiation (Watts / m ²)					8	4-7	0-3
	Strong	Moderate	Slight	Overcast				
	>600	300-600	<300	N=8 Oktas				
<=3	A	A-B	B	C	D	D	F	F/G
4-5	A-B	B	C	C	D	D	E	F
6-9	B	B-C	C	C	D	D	D	E
10-12	C	C-D	D	D	D	D	D	D
>12	C	D	D	D	D	D	D	D

NOTES

- 1). Category G occurs with Total Cloud Amount 0 or 1 okta and Wind Speed 0 or 1 knot.
- 2). Dawn is the period within 1 hour of Sunrise
- 3). Dusk is the period within 1 hour before Sunset

MAP SHOWING STATIONS WITH SURFACE DATA SUITABLE FOR PRODUCING LONG TERM STABILITY FREQUENCY TABLES

PASQUILL STABILITY CATEGORY FREQUENCY ANALYSIS

EXAMPLE OF SECTION 1

JANUARY - FREQUENCIES OF EACH STABILITY IN EACH HOUR

HOUR	A	A-B	B	B-C	C	C-D	D	E	F	G	TOTAL
00	0	0	0	0	0	0	231	33	40	6	310
01	0	0	0	0	0	0	226	42	39	3	310
02	0	0	0	0	0	0	228	37	41	4	310
03	0	0	0	0	0	0	227	31	47	5	310
04	0	0	0	0	0	0	231	24	50	5	310
05	0	0	0	0	0	0	217	37	49	7	310
06	0	0	0	0	0	0	220	27	61	2	310
07	0	0	0	0	0	0	220	40	48	2	310
08	0	0	0	0	0	0	243	28	34	5	310
09	0	0	19	0	41	0	250	0	0	0	310
10	0	0	40	0	125	0	145	0	0	0	310
11	0	0	37	0	117	0	156	0	0	0	310
12	0	0	34	2	103	0	171	0	0	0	310
13	0	0	29	0	113	0	168	0	0	0	310
14	0	0	26	0	114	0	170	0	0	0	310
15	0	0	21	0	77	0	212	0	0	0	310
16	0	0	0	0	0	0	283	13	14	0	310
17	0	0	0	0	0	0	224	39	46	1	310
18	0	0	0	0	0	0	221	41	45	3	310
19	0	0	0	0	0	0	226	35	45	4	310
20	0	0	0	0	0	0	233	35	42	0	310
21	0	0	0	0	0	0	227	39	41	3	310
22	0	0	0	0	0	0	229	35	43	3	310
23	0	0	0	0	0	0	229	36	39	6	310
TOTAL	0	0	206	2	690	0	5187	572	724	59	7440

JANUARY - PERCENTAGE FREQUENCIES

HOUR	A	A-B	B	B-C	C	C-D	D	E	F	G	TOTAL
00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	74.52	10.65	12.90	1.94	100.00
01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	72.90	13.55	12.58	0.97	100.00
02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	73.55	11.94	13.23	1.29	100.00
03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	73.23	10.00	15.16	1.61	100.00
04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	74.52	7.74	16.13	1.61	100.00
05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	70.00	11.94	15.81	2.26	100.00
06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	70.97	8.71	19.68	0.65	100.00
07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	70.97	12.90	15.48	0.65	100.00
08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	78.39	9.03	10.97	1.61	100.00
09	0.00	0.00	6.13	0.00	13.23	0.00	80.65	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
10	0.00	0.00	12.90	0.00	40.32	0.00	46.77	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
11	0.00	0.00	11.94	0.00	37.74	0.00	50.32	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
12	0.00	0.00	10.97	0.65	33.23	0.00	55.16	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
13	0.00	0.00	9.35	0.00	36.45	0.00	54.19	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
14	0.00	0.00	8.39	0.00	36.77	0.00	54.84	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
15	0.00	0.00	6.77	0.00	24.84	0.00	68.39	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
16	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	91.29	4.19	4.52	0.00	100.00
17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	72.26	12.58	14.84	0.32	100.00
18	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	71.29	13.23	14.52	0.97	100.00
19	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	72.90	11.29	14.52	1.29	100.00
20	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	75.16	11.29	13.55	0.00	100.00
21	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	73.23	12.58	13.23	0.97	100.00
22	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	73.87	11.29	13.87	0.97	100.00
23	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	73.87	11.61	12.58	1.94	100.00
TOTAL	0.00	0.00	2.77	0.03	9.27	0.00	69.72	7.69	9.73	0.79	100.00

PASQUILL STABILITY CATEGORY FREQUENCY ANALYSIS EXAMPLE OF SECTION 2

FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF CATEGORY - C

HOUR	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP	OCT	NOV	DEC	TOTAL
05	0	0	0	0	53	163	91	0	0	0	0	0	307
06	0	0	0	71	161	170	166	121	0	0	0	0	689
07	0	0	68	151	140	151	149	170	121	0	0	0	950
08	0	43	140	122	102	123	120	133	139	100	0	0	1022
09	41	119	110	77	92	109	96	100	125	150	83	0	1102
10	125	109	98	74	75	49	61	79	101	126	138	126	1161
11	117	98	75	62	41	42	35	51	80	107	117	127	952
12	103	88	74	65	47	44	35	45	77	104	114	120	916
13	113	98	71	58	50	52	39	61	89	103	120	114	968
14	114	94	82	63	56	46	38	69	89	113	129	113	1006
15	77	91	96	72	77	78	74	89	115	135	117	0	1021
16	0	73	104	96	81	81	81	104	127	126	0	0	873
17	0	0	78	117	105	104	109	159	148	5	0	0	825
18	0	0	0	102	154	147	163	166	13	0	0	0	745
19	0	0	0	0	119	173	184	3	0	0	0	0	479
TOTAL	690	813	996	1130	1353	1532	1441	1350	1224	1069	818	600	13016

PERCENTAGE FREQUENCIES, CATEGORY - C

HOUR	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP	OCT	NOV	DEC	TOTAL
05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	17.26	53.09	29.64	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
06	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.30	23.37	24.67	24.09	17.56	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
07	0.00	0.00	7.16	15.89	14.74	15.89	15.68	17.89	12.74	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
08	0.00	4.21	13.70	11.94	9.98	12.04	11.74	13.01	13.60	9.78	0.00	0.00	100.00
09	3.72	10.80	9.98	6.99	8.35	9.89	8.71	9.07	11.34	13.61	7.53	0.00	100.00
10	10.77	9.39	8.44	6.37	6.46	4.22	5.25	6.80	8.70	10.85	11.89	10.85	100.00
11	12.29	10.29	7.88	6.51	4.31	4.41	3.68	5.36	8.40	11.24	12.29	13.34	100.00
12	11.24	9.61	8.08	7.10	5.13	4.80	3.82	4.91	8.41	11.35	12.45	13.10	100.00
13	11.67	10.12	7.33	5.99	5.17	5.37	4.03	6.30	9.19	10.64	12.40	11.78	100.00
14	11.33	9.34	8.15	6.26	5.57	4.57	3.78	6.86	8.85	11.23	12.82	11.23	100.00
15	7.54	8.91	9.40	7.05	7.54	7.64	7.25	8.72	11.26	13.22	11.46	0.00	100.00
16	0.00	8.36	11.91	11.00	9.28	9.28	9.28	11.91	14.55	14.43	0.00	0.00	100.00
17	0.00	0.00	9.45	14.18	12.73	12.61	13.21	19.27	17.94	0.61	0.00	0.00	100.00
18	0.00	0.00	0.00	13.69	20.67	19.73	21.88	22.28	1.74	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
19	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	24.84	36.12	38.41	0.63	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
TOTAL	5.30	6.25	7.65	8.68	10.39	11.77	11.07	10.37	9.40	8.21	6.28	4.61	100.00

PASQUILL STABILITY CATEGORY FREQUENCY ANALYSIS EXAMPLE OF SECTION 3 (16 SECTORS)

PERCENTAGE FREQUENCIES OF MODIFIED PASQUILL STABILITY CATEGORIES CONTINUED FOR JANUARY

D	CALM	1.022	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.022
	1- 3 KT 1	0.000	0.129	0.082	0.153	0.288	0.368	0.360	0.441	0.582	0.929	0.573	0.336	0.422	0.349	0.212	0.207	0.163	5.591
	4- 6 KT 2	0.000	0.286	0.257	0.280	0.395	0.383	0.456	0.542	0.902	1.015	0.539	0.343	0.316	0.215	0.249	0.376	0.290	6.841
	7-10 KT 3	0.000	0.289	0.383	0.605	0.461	0.609	0.535	0.847	2.226	4.026	2.655	1.606	1.175	0.840	0.566	0.618	0.317	17.755
	11-16 KT 4	0.000	0.116	0.476	0.825	0.427	0.603	0.524	0.671	1.819	5.798	4.724	2.777	3.648	2.766	1.323	0.817	0.216	27.527
	17-98 KT 5	0.000	0.000	0.094	0.409	0.234	0.067	0.175	0.136	0.824	1.793	1.980	0.980	1.137	2.034	0.949	0.161	0.012	10.981
	ALL	1.022	0.820	1.292	2.270	1.802	2.030	2.048	2.634	6.351	13.560	10.470	6.042	6.698	6.203	3.298	2.179	1.000	69.718
E	CALM	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	1- 3 KT 1	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	4- 6 KT 2	0.000	0.200	0.167	0.202	0.113	0.181	0.175	0.215	0.519	0.833	0.478	0.243	0.247	0.173	0.227	0.185	0.169	4.328
	7-10 KT 3	0.000	0.044	0.112	0.067	0.066	0.082	0.094	0.095	0.341	0.743	0.575	0.401	0.263	0.069	0.098	0.253	0.060	3.360
	11-16 KT 4	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	17-98 KT 5	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	ALL	0.000	0.243	0.277	0.269	0.179	0.263	0.269	0.310	0.860	1.577	1.054	0.644	0.511	0.242	0.324	0.437	0.230	7.688
F/G	CALM	1.532	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.532
	1- 3 KT 1	0.000	0.267	0.168	0.153	0.313	0.456	0.397	0.383	0.583	0.684	0.642	0.422	0.387	0.409	0.474	0.516	0.484	6.734
	4- 6 KT 2	0.000	0.087	0.079	0.136	0.093	0.148	0.153	0.159	0.220	0.329	0.163	0.078	0.062	0.022	0.069	0.257	0.206	2.258
	7-10 KT 3	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	11-16 KT 4	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	17-98 KT 5	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	ALL	1.532	0.355	0.247	0.289	0.405	0.603	0.550	0.542	0.804	1.013	0.805	0.499	0.449	0.430	0.543	0.773	0.690	10.524
ALL	CALM	2.849	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	2.849
	1- 3 KT 1	0.000	0.617	0.324	0.382	0.711	1.050	0.980	1.066	1.429	2.137	1.767	1.106	1.066	1.019	0.858	0.965	0.927	16.398
	4- 6 KT 2	0.000	0.691	0.636	0.757	0.777	0.913	0.862	1.102	2.043	2.777	1.523	0.882	0.797	0.570	0.716	1.070	0.852	16.962
	7-10 KT 3	0.000	0.441	0.640	0.781	0.610	0.804	0.798	1.147	3.017	5.692	3.797	2.398	1.718	1.043	0.759	1.157	0.483	25.282
	11-16 KT 4	0.000	0.116	0.476	0.825	0.427	0.603	0.524	0.671	1.819	5.798	4.724	2.777	3.648	2.766	1.323	0.817	0.216	27.527
	17-98 KT 5	0.000	0.000	0.094	0.409	0.234	0.067	0.175	0.136	0.824	1.793	1.980	0.980	1.137	2.034	0.949	0.161	0.012	10.981
	ALL	2.849	1.863	2.169	3.152	2.757	3.435	3.339	4.120	9.130	18.198	13.790	8.142	8.364	7.430	4.603	4.171	2.491	100.000

STAB. WIND CAT. SPEED	CALM	N	NNE	NE	ENE	E	ESE	SE	SSE	S	SSW	SW	WSW	W	WNW	NW	NNW	TOTAL
		349	012	035	057	079	102	125	147	169	192	215	237	259	282	305	327	
		- 011	- 034	- 056	- 078	- 101	- 124	- 146	- 168	- 191	- 214	- 236	- 258	- 281	- 304	- 326	- 348	

16 SECTOR PASQUILL STABILITY FREQUENCY ANALYSIS SUITABLE FOR ISC LONG TERM DISPERSION MODEL

The Pasquill Stability Categories were defined to describe the stability of the lowest layers of the atmosphere so that they could be used for estimating the dispersion of air pollution released from the ground or from industrial stacks.

There are 6 categories for this analysis from A (very unstable) through D (neutral) to F (very stable).

Category A (Very Unstable) occurs typically on a warm sunny summer afternoon with light winds and almost cloudless skies when there is strong solar heating of the ground and the air immediately above the surface. Bubbles of warm air rise from the ground in thermals. The lapse rate near the surface is super - adiabatic (i.e. it exceeds the dry adiabatic lapse rate).

Category D (Neutral) occurs in cloudy conditions or whenever there is a strong surface wind to cause vigorous mechanical mixing of the lower atmosphere. This category occurs both day and night. The period immediately after sunrise and immediately before sunset is normally considered neutral. The lapse rate is equal to or less than the dry adiabatic lapse rate.

Category F (Very Stable) occurs typically on a cold clear calm night when there is strong cooling of the ground and the lowest layers of the atmosphere by long wave radiation to space. There is a strong inversion of temperature. Category G only occurs at night. Category E also only occurs at night normally with a slight or moderate inversion of temperature.

The Stability Categories are estimated from the total cloud amount, wind speed and time of year.

During the day an estimate is made of the incident solar radiation and this is combined with the wind speed to estimate the Stability Category.

At night the Stability Category is a simple function of cloud cover and wind speed.

Section 1 gives the frequency and percentage frequency distribution of the Stability Categories as a function of wind direction and wind speed for each month and the whole year.

The wind speed classes are 0-3, 4-6, 7-10, 11-16, 17-21, greater than 21 knots (corresponding to the Beaufort Forces 1/2 combined, 3, 4, 5, 6 or greater). The wind direction is the direction from which the wind blows, and is classified in sixteen, 22.5 degree direction sectors, agreeing with the 16 cardinal points of the compass, and calm.

The wind direction is recorded at the Met. Station to the nearest 10 degrees from True North. Therefore the sector labelled N (for example) actually contains the observations recorded at 350, 360 and 010 degrees, and the sector labelled NNE contains the observations at 020 and 030 and so on.

Section 2 gives the percentage frequency distribution of the Stability Categories as a function of wind speed for each month and the whole year. This section is produced for direct input into the ISC Long Term Model. The wind speed classes are 0-3, 4-6, 7-10, 11-16, 17-21, greater than 21 knots.

16 SECTOR PASQUILL STABILITY FREQUENCY ANALYSIS

SUITABLE FOR ISC LONG TERM DISPERSION MODEL

Example of Section 1

PAGE . STATION NAME - - ANALYSIS PERIOD - 1 1 89 TO 31 12 89
 - FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION - JUNE

STABILITY CATEGORY	WIND SECTOR	WIND SPEED(KNOTS)						TOTAL	AVG SPD
		0-3	4-6	7-10	11-16	17-21	GREATER THAN 21		
ALL	CALM	28	0	0	0	0	0	28	0.0
	N	15	37	43	8	0	0	103	6.6
	NNE	10	38	20	5	0	0	73	5.9
	NE	7	21	25	4	0	0	57	6.4
	ENE	2	3	10	0	0	0	15	7.3
	E	0	6	6	5	0	0	17	8.3
	ESE	2	7	7	8	0	0	25	8.4
	SE	1	14	5	5	0	0	25	6.9
	SSE	3	7	10	2	0	0	23	7.0
	S	7	11	23	4	0	0	45	7.1
	SSW	6	18	20	12	0	0	57	7.4
	SW	8	18	27	21	0	0	74	8.3
	USW	7	10	15	6	0	0	39	7.1
	W	2	10	13	2	0	0	28	7.0
	WNW	15	10	6	4	0	0	34	5.2
	NW	6	8	7	1	0	0	22	5.5
	NNW	18	23	16	0	0	0	57	5.0
	TOTAL	137	241	254	88	0	0	720	6.5

- PERCENTAGE FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION (NORMALISED) - JUNE

ALL	CALM	0.0388889	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0388889
	N	0.0206944	0.0519444	0.0597222	0.0109722	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.1431944
	NNE	0.0136111	0.0533333	0.0275000	0.0066667	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.1008333
	NE	0.0094444	0.0284722	0.0345833	0.0061111	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0784722
	ENE	0.0027778	0.0038889	0.0144444	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0209722
	E	0.0000000	0.0087500	0.0088889	0.0066667	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0241667
	ESE	0.0026389	0.0101389	0.0098611	0.0115278	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0340278
	SE	0.0018056	0.0191667	0.0068056	0.0069444	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0345833
	SSE	0.0047222	0.0091667	0.0144444	0.0033333	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0316667
	S	0.0091667	0.0158333	0.0320833	0.0054167	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0625000
	SSW	0.0088889	0.0254167	0.0283333	0.0166667	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0791667
	SW	0.0111111	0.0248611	0.0380556	0.0293056	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.1033333
	USW	0.0095833	0.0140278	0.0209722	0.0088889	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0534722
	W	0.0031944	0.0143056	0.0184722	0.0031944	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0388889
	WNW	0.0202778	0.0136111	0.0076389	0.0050000	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0465278
	NW	0.0083333	0.0109722	0.0094444	0.0019444	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0305556
	NNW	0.0255556	0.0313889	0.0219444	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0000000	0.0788888
	TOTAL	0.1902778	0.3347222	0.3527777	0.1222222	0.0000000	0.0000000	1.0000000

16 SECTOR PASQUILL STABILITY FREQUENCY ANALYSIS

SUITABLE FOR ISC LONG TERM DISPERSION MODEL

Example of Section 2

N A	.00000	.00181	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
NNE A	.00000	.00181	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
NE A	.00000	.00292	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
ENE A	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
E A	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
ESE A	.00139	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
SE A	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
SSE A	.00000	.00139	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
S A	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
SSW A	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
SW A	.00000	.00014	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
WSW A	.00000	.00125	.00139	.00000	.00000	.00000
W A	.00000	.00083	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
WNW A	.00000	.00056	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
NW A	.00000	.00139	.00139	.00000	.00000	.00000
NNW A	.00000	.00194	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
N B	.00361	.00889	.00819	.00083	.00000	.00000
NNE B	.00139	.00986	.00264	.00056	.00000	.00000
NE B	.00000	.00764	.01056	.00000	.00000	.00000
ENE B	.00278	.00139	.00764	.00000	.00000	.00000
E B	.00000	.00139	.00222	.00000	.00000	.00000
ESE B	.00125	.00125	.00194	.00000	.00000	.00000
SE B	.00014	.00292	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
SSE B	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
S B	.00000	.00083	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
SSW B	.00139	.00181	.00403	.00125	.00000	.00000
SW B	.00014	.00181	.00458	.00014	.00000	.00000
WSW B	.00125	.00264	.00181	.00000	.00000	.00000
W B	.00000	.00222	.00597	.00000	.00000	.00000
WNW B	.00000	.00319	.00194	.00000	.00000	.00000
NW B	.00000	.00194	.00139	.00000	.00000	.00000
NNW B	.00194	.00250	.00153	.00000	.00000	.00000
N C	.00875	.00639	.03000	.00361	.00000	.00000
NNE C	.00194	.00972	.01042	.00056	.00000	.00000
NE C	.00000	.00750	.01611	.00556	.00000	.00000
ENE C	.00000	.00000	.00361	.00000	.00000	.00000
E C	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
ESE C	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
SE C	.00014	.00000	.00528	.00139	.00000	.00000
SSE C	.00125	.00000	.01236	.00333	.00000	.00000
S C	.00139	.00222	.01514	.00458	.00000	.00000
SSW C	.00000	.00681	.00847	.00431	.00000	.00000
SW C	.00000	.00222	.00681	.00625	.00000	.00000
WSW C	.00278	.00361	.00764	.00528	.00000	.00000
W C	.00000	.00181	.00736	.00000	.00000	.00000
WNW C	.00278	.00389	.00111	.00000	.00000	.00000
NW C	.00139	.00125	.00292	.00000	.00000	.00000
NNW C	.00056	.00750	.00625	.00000	.00000	.00000

16 SECTOR PASQUILL STABILITY FREQUENCY ANALYSIS

SUITABLE FOR ISC LONG TERM DISPERSION MODEL

Example of Section 2 (continued)

N D	.01778	.01431	.01528	.00639	.00000	.00000
NNE D	.00153	.01750	.01014	.00417	.00000	.00000
NE D	.00278	.00111	.00736	.00056	.00000	.00000
ENE D	.00000	.00125	.00194	.00000	.00000	.00000
E D	.00000	.00278	.00083	.00569	.00000	.00000
ESE D	.00000	.00125	.00264	.01097	.00000	.00000
SE D	.00000	.00458	.00153	.00556	.00000	.00000
SSE D	.00194	.00222	.00208	.00000	.00000	.00000
S D	.00264	.00667	.01708	.00083	.00000	.00000
SSW D	.00222	.00708	.01194	.01111	.00000	.00000
SW D	.00181	.00889	.02222	.02292	.00000	.00000
WSW D	.00319	.00528	.00833	.00361	.00000	.00000
W D	.00222	.00542	.00347	.00319	.00000	.00000
WNW D	.00917	.00194	.00153	.00500	.00000	.00000
NW D	.00431	.00194	.00208	.00194	.00000	.00000
NNW D	.01306	.01264	.00833	.00000	.00000	.00000
N E	.00000	.01361	.00625	.00000	.00000	.00000
NNE E	.00361	.00694	.00431	.00139	.00000	.00000
NE E	.00194	.00500	.00056	.00000	.00000	.00000
ENE E	.00000	.00125	.00125	.00000	.00000	.00000
E E	.00000	.00181	.00569	.00083	.00000	.00000
ESE E	.00000	.00361	.00542	.00056	.00000	.00000
SE E	.00000	.00597	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
SSE E	.00000	.00500	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
S E	.00000	.00431	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
SSW E	.00125	.00542	.00389	.00000	.00000	.00000
SW E	.00153	.01153	.00458	.00000	.00000	.00000
WSW E	.00000	.00000	.00194	.00000	.00000	.00000
W E	.00000	.00222	.00181	.00000	.00000	.00000
WNW E	.00000	.00194	.00319	.00000	.00000	.00000
NW E	.00000	.00278	.00153	.00000	.00000	.00000
NNW E	.00000	.00528	.00569	.00000	.00000	.00000
N F	.02958	.00708	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
NNE F	.00500	.00750	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
NE F	.00472	.00431	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
INF F	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
E F	.00000	.00278	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
ESE F	.00000	.00403	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
SE F	.00139	.00569	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
SSE F	.00153	.00056	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
S F	.00528	.00181	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
SSW F	.00403	.00431	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
SW F	.00764	.00042	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
WSW F	.00250	.00139	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
W F	.00083	.00181	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
WNW F	.00833	.00222	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
NW F	.00264	.00181	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000
NNW F	.01014	.00181	.00000	.00000	.00000	.00000

BOUNDARY LAYER DEPTH FREQUENCY ANALYSIS

This is an analysis of Boundary Layer Depth and Pasquill Stability Category.

The output is in the form of two sets of tables.

SECTION 1

- a) Frequency of each stability category as a function of the time of day for each month and for the whole year.
- b) Frequency of boundary layer thickness as a function of the time of day for each month and for the whole year.

SECTION 2

Mean percentage frequency of occurrence of each atmospheric stability as a function of wind direction and wind speed from each month and for the whole year.

MONTH JANUARY

BOUNDARY LAYER THICKNESS (METRES)	PASQUILL STABILITY CATEGORY							TOTAL	
	A	B	C	D(DAY)	D(NIGHT)	E	F		G
0.0 - 0.0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.1 - 200.0	0	0	0	58	0	212	225	295	790
200.1 - 400.0	0	0	18	264	0	302	216	0	800
400.1 - 600.0	0	0	59	338	0	561	139	0	1097
600.1 - 800.0	0	0	31	314	262	443	0	0	1050
800.1 - 1000.0	0	0	10	368	273	334	0	0	985
1000.1 - 1200.0	0	0	3	302	302	153	0	0	760
1200.1 - 1400.0	0	0	0	273	313	26	0	0	612
1400.1 - 1600.0	0	0	0	162	303	0	0	0	465
1600.1 - 1800.0	0	0	0	160	213	0	0	0	373
1800.1 - 2000.0	0	0	0	89	153	0	0	0	242
2000.1 - 9999.9	0	0	0	131	135	0	0	0	266
TOTAL	0	0	121	2459	1954	2031	580	295	7440
MEAN (METRES)	0.0	0.0	564.3	1008.0	1320.5	584.2	248.8	37.2	869.3

PASQUILL STABILITY AND BOUNDARY LAYER DEPTH ANALYSIS

MONTH JANUARY

FREQUENCY OF PASQUILL STABILITY CATEGORY AS A FUNCTION OF WIND SPEED.

WIND SPEED (KNOTS)	PASQUILL STABILITY CATEGORY								TOTAL
	A	B	C	D(DAY)	D(NIGHT)	E	F	G	
0	0	0	7	49	0	51	43	102	252
1-3	0	0	48	299	0	371	220	193	1131
4-6	0	0	46	485	126	757	317	0	1731
7-10	0	0	20	718	629	766	0	0	2133
11-16	0	0	0	713	880	86	0	0	1679
17-98	0	0	0	195	319	0	0	0	514
ALL	0	0	121	2459	1954	2031	580	295	7440

AVERAGE BOUNDARY LAYER THICKNESS ANALYSIS

AVERAGE BOUNDARY LAYER THICKNESS (METRES) AS A FUNCTION OF PASQUILL STABILITY CATEGORY AND WIND SPEED.

WIND SPEED (KNOTS)	PASQUILL STABILITY CATEGORY								MEAN (METRES)
	A	B	C	D(DAY)	D(NIGHT)	E	F	G	
0	0.0	0.0	408.2	193.7	0.0	133.0	107.1	23.0	103.5
1-3	0.0	0.0	436.6	345.2	0.0	172.4	92.9	44.7	192.1
4-6	0.0	0.0	600.1	579.4	644.5	500.1	376.2	0.0	512.8
7-10	0.0	0.0	843.0	933.1	955.8	833.3	0.0	0.0	902.9
11-16	0.0	0.0	0.0	1407.8	1428.1	1151.8	0.0	0.0	1405.1
17-98	0.0	0.0	0.0	2113.2	2011.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	2050.0
ALL	0.0	0.0	564.3	1008.0	1320.5	584.2	248.8	37.2	869.3

STATION NAME - - ANALYSIS PERIOD -		- MEAN PERCENTAGE FREQUENCY OF TIME -- JANUARY --													
STABILITY CATEGORY	WIND SPEED (KNOTS)	WIND DIRECTION (DEGREES)													
		CALM	346	016	046	076	106	136	166	196	226	256	286	316	ALL DIRNS
A	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	1-3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	4-6	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	7-10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	ALL	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
B	0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	1-3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	4-6	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	7-10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	ALL	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
C	0	0.09	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.09
	1-3	0.00	0.07	0.05	0.03	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.11	0.05	0.09	0.16	0.05	0.65
	4-6	0.00	0.04	0.09	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.00	0.04	0.08	0.05	0.12	0.07	0.00	0.62
	7-10	0.00	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.08	0.05	0.08	0.03	0.00	0.27
	ALL	0.09	0.13	0.17	0.09	0.07	0.07	0.00	0.09	0.19	0.19	0.24	0.23	0.05	1.63
D	0	0.66	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.66
	1-3	0.00	0.60	0.46	0.15	0.07	0.20	0.36	0.35	0.39	0.42	0.30	0.43	0.30	4.02
	4-6	0.00	0.58	1.05	0.32	0.38	0.66	0.59	1.05	0.94	0.99	0.54	0.54	0.58	8.21
	7-10	0.00	0.91	1.44	0.87	0.98	1.14	0.99	3.37	3.45	2.53	1.17	0.85	0.39	18.10
	ALL	0.66	2.66	4.74	1.80	2.24	2.53	3.04	7.72	12.31	12.11	4.66	3.08	1.76	59.31
E	0	0.69	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.69
	1-3	0.00	0.55	0.77	0.17	0.20	0.23	0.27	0.38	0.59	0.32	0.66	0.32	0.52	4.99
	4-6	0.00	0.81	1.28	0.54	0.54	0.66	0.58	1.37	1.53	0.90	0.87	0.51	0.59	10.17
	7-10	0.00	0.50	0.54	0.19	0.51	0.27	0.17	0.90	2.34	2.45	1.28	0.78	0.38	10.30
	ALL	0.69	1.92	2.61	0.91	1.30	1.16	1.02	2.65	4.56	4.10	3.16	1.72	1.51	27.30
F	0	0.58	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.58
	1-3	0.00	0.40	0.19	0.05	0.05	0.12	0.20	0.38	0.30	0.26	0.35	0.35	0.31	2.96
	4-6	0.00	0.34	0.52	0.11	0.15	0.07	0.12	0.51	0.74	0.58	0.50	0.26	0.38	4.26
	7-10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	ALL	0.58	0.74	0.71	0.16	0.20	0.19	0.32	0.89	1.03	0.83	0.85	0.60	0.69	7.80
G	0	1.37	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.37
	1-3	0.00	0.27	0.22	0.08	0.05	0.12	0.16	0.12	0.30	0.22	0.42	0.34	0.31	2.59
	4-6	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	7-10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	ALL	1.37	0.27	0.22	0.08	0.05	0.12	0.16	0.12	0.30	0.22	0.42	0.34	0.31	3.97
ALL	0	3.39	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3.39
	1-3	0.00	1.90	1.68	0.48	0.38	0.69	0.99	1.24	1.68	1.26	1.81	1.60	1.49	15.20
	4-6	0.00	1.76	2.94	1.01	1.09	1.44	1.29	2.97	3.29	2.53	2.03	1.37	1.55	23.27
	7-10	0.00	1.44	2.00	1.09	1.53	1.41	1.17	4.31	5.79	5.05	2.47	1.63	0.77	28.67
	ALL	3.39	5.73	8.45	3.05	3.87	4.06	4.54	11.47	18.39	17.45	9.33	5.97	4.31	100.00

BOUNDARY LAYER DEPTH FREQUENCY ANALYSIS EXAMPLE OF SECTION 2

UK-ADMS

There is a general trend in dispersion modelling away from models based on Pasquill Stability towards models which require surface sensible heat flux and boundary layer depth.

An example of such a model is UK-ADMS, developed by Cambridge Environmental Research Consultants Ltd (CERC), National Power PLC and the Meteorological Office.

The Met. Office provides data analyses suitable for these models from a range of observing sites.

UK-ADMS is able to analyse individual events or consider the impact of long period emissions using meteorological statistics generated from longer periods. All data provided is in a format suitable for direct use by the model.

The model runs under Microsoft Window 3.0 on any '386' or '486' personal computer with a co-processor and 4 MB or more memory. It comprises of a number of individual modules.

For more information and a separate brochure please contact the Environmental Consultancy Services (Air Pollution), (address and contacts given at the front of this brochure).

For further information on the UK-ADMS model please contact:-

Phone (0223) 357773 Fax (0223) 357492

CERC Ltd
3D King's Parade
Cambridge
CB2 1SJ
England

MAP SHOWING STATIONS WITH SURFACE DATA SUITABLE FOR INPUT INTO THE UK-ADMS MODEL

FREQUENCY ANALYSIS SUITABLE FOR ALMANAC DISPERSION MODEL

This is an analysis of wind speed, wind direction and total cloud amount. It is split into 3 basic sections according to the seasons as follows:-

Section 1 :- Months 3,4,9,10

Section 2 :- Months 5,6,7,8

Section 3 :- Months 1,2,11,12

Each section gives the frequency and percentage frequency distribution of total cloud amount split into classes containing cloud values between 0-6 Oktas and 7-9 Oktas as a function of wind speed and wind direction.

The tables show, for each cloud group indicated above:-

- a) The number of hours with the speed and direction in that category.
- b) This number expressed as a percentage.

The wind speed classes are 0, 1-3, 4-6, knots etc to correspond with the Beaufort Forces 1, 2, 3, etc.

The wind direction is the direction from which the wind blows, and is classified in twelve, 30 degree direction sectors.

The period of the analysis is normally 10 years and is shown at the top of each section along with the name, latitude and longitude and height A.M.S.L of the station used in the analysis.

ALMANAC FREQUENCY ANALYSIS

Example (Continued)

PERCENTAGE FREQUENCY TABLE

		WIND DIRECTION (DEGREES TRUE)											TOTAL	
		346	16	46	76	106	136	166	196	226	256	286		316
		15	45	75	105	135	165	195	225	255	285	315	345	
WIND SPEED (KNOTS)														
	0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3
1 TO	3	0.6	0.8	0.4	1.4	1.9	3.7	2.0	0.8	1.1	1.4	1.3	0.8	16.3
4 TO	6	0.7	0.2	0.6	0.7	1.3	2.0	4.3	2.7	2.4	3.6	0.9	0.5	19.9
7 TO	10	1.5	0.6	0.5	0.5	0.7	1.2	2.9	3.6	2.7	5.0	3.5	1.4	24.0
11 TO	16	1.0	1.6	0.4	0.0	0.2	0.0	1.0	4.3	3.8	9.4	2.6	2.1	26.4
17 TO	21	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	1.9	1.9	3.4	0.7	0.7	9.1
22 TO	27	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7	1.0	1.0	0.2	0.1	2.9
28 TO	33	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
34 TO	40	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
41 TO	47	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
48 TO	55	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
56 TO	63	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
64 TO	99	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
TOTALS		3.8	3.2	2.1	2.6	4.0	6.9	10.2	14.0	12.9	23.7	9.3	5.7	100.0

MAP SHOWING ANEMOGRAPH STATIONS WITH AT LEAST
10/15 YEARS COMPUTER ARCHIVE DATA

EXPLANATION OF THE WASP ANALYSIS

(WIND ATLAS ANALYSIS AND APPLICATION PROGRAM)

The Met. Office has an extensive computer archive of wind observations that includes about 150 locations with at least 10 years of hourly measurements of speed and direction. When an estimate of the wind climatology is required for a specific site then a direct analysis of the record from one of these Met. Office stations is often sufficient. However there are occasions when there is no station that is sufficiently representative of the site in question. In these cases the Met. Office can offer an estimation service, WASP.

It is based on methods described in the European Wind Atlas and comprises physical and statistical models of how the wind is affected by the underlying surface.

The starting point is a summary, typically based on 10 years of hourly mean wind speeds and directions, of the climate at a Met. Office Station. Access to high resolution topography and land use databases allows detailed descriptions to be obtained of the terrain surrounding both the Met. Office station and the site under evaluation. These are used in conjunction with WASP to derive the required climatology at any location in Great Britain. Where appropriate the effects of individual obstacles can also be included.

Each analysis results in a frequency table and wind rose, examples of each are shown in the next few pages. Although in most cases all the data are analysed together, it is also possible to produce estimates for individual months or seasons.

The 3 Factors required to run a WASP Analysis :-

The Grid Reference of the Site

The Height above Ground Level

The Period of the Year for which the Climatology is Required

Applications

Some examples of the uses to which these techniques can be put include:-

Assessing the potential of a site for wind energy generation.

Identifying the wind regime at sites where the dispersion of pollutants is of concern.

Assessing the impact of wind on structures at exposed sites eg bridges.

EXPLANATION OF THE WASP FREQUENCY ANALYSIS AND WIND ROSE

Wind Frequency Analysis

The table shows for the ten year period the number of hours expressed as a percentage with the wind speed and direction in various categories.

Wind directions are measured to the nearest 10 degrees from True North and relate to the direction from which the wind is blowing. For example:-

Direction 360 degrees = Wind Blowing from North

Direction 090 degrees = Wind Blowing from East

Direction 180 degrees = Wind Blowing from South

Direction 270 degrees = Wind Blowing from West

The size of each wind sector is 300 centred on the value indicated in the analysis (eg 0 is the 300 sector 350 - 010)

The wind speed ranges are in metres/sec

For converting speeds 1 m/s = 3.6 km/h = 1.943 knots = 2.237 mph

Wind Rose

The wind rose is an average for the ten years. North is at the top of the page as you read it. There are 12 arms coming from the central circle of the diagram, each representing a 30 degree segment of wind direction. The length of each arm is proportional to the amount of time, in hours, the wind blew from that particular segment.

Wind directions are expressed in degrees from true North and represent the direction from which the wind is blowing.

EXAMPLE WIND FREQUENCY ANALYSIS FOR WASP

WASP WIND FREQUENCY ANALYSIS FOR SITE NEAR
ESTIMATED FROM OBSERVATIONAL DATA FOR

- NGR 50
- 1983-92

WIND SPEED	30 DEGREE SECTOR CENTRED ON								ALL DIRECTIONS				
	0	30	60	90	120	150	180	210	240	270	300	330	
<=1 H/S	1.28	1.01	1.12	1.98	1.94	1.51	1.45	1.25	1.67	1.63	2.11	2.42	19.4
2 H/S	1.21	1.02	1.33	1.69	1.48	1.48	1.98	1.67	1.85	1.95	1.94	1.68	19.3
3 H/S	1.04	0.90	1.30	1.45	1.15	1.30	2.12	1.82	1.90	2.12	1.78	1.29	18.2
4 H/S	0.75	0.67	1.04	1.09	0.78	0.96	1.81	1.63	1.70	2.00	1.43	0.88	14.8
5 H/S	0.48	0.43	0.70	0.76	0.48	0.63	1.31	1.26	1.38	1.71	1.06	0.57	10.8
6 H/S	0.27	0.25	0.42	0.49	0.28	0.36	0.82	0.87	1.04	1.35	0.73	0.34	7.2
7 H/S	0.14	0.13	0.22	0.29	0.15	0.19	0.45	0.53	0.74	1.00	0.48	0.20	4.5
8 H/S	0.07	0.06	0.10	0.17	0.07	0.09	0.22	0.30	0.49	0.70	0.29	0.11	2.7
9 H/S	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.09	0.04	0.04	0.09	0.15	0.31	0.46	0.17	0.06	1.5
10 H/S	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.07	0.19	0.29	0.10	0.03	0.8
11 H/S	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.11	0.17	0.05	0.01	0.4
12 H/S	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.06	0.10	0.03	0.01	0.2
13 H/S	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.06	0.01	0.00	0.1
14 H/S	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.0
15 H/S	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.0
16 H/S	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.0
17 H/S	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0
18 H/S	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0
19 H/S	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0
20 H/S	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0
21 H/S	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0
22 H/S	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0
23 H/S	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0
24 H/S	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0
25 H/S	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0
>=26 H/S	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0
TOTAL	5.3	4.5	6.3	8.1	6.4	6.6	10.3	9.6	11.5	13.6	10.2	7.6	100.0
MEAN SPEED	3.0	3.0	3.3	3.2	2.7	3.0	3.5	3.8	4.1	4.5	3.5	2.7	3.5

NOTES

1. THIS ANALYSIS IS BASED ON HOURLY MEAN VALUES OF WIND SPEED AND DIRECTION.
2. OCCASIONS OF CALM HAVE NOT BEEN INCLUDED IN THE ANALYSIS.
3. THE FREQUENCIES ARE EXPRESSED AS PERCENTAGES OF ALL OCCASIONS.
4. A FREQUENCY OF 0.01% IS EQUIVALENT TO APPROXIMATELY 1 HOUR PER YEAR - RARER EVENTS CANNOT BE RELIABLY ESTIMATED USING THIS TECHNIQUE.
5. MEAN SPEEDS ARE IN UNITS OF M/S.

A WIND ROSE FOR

WASP ESTIMATE BASED ON HRLY MEAN WINDS -

(83-92)

EXAMPLE WIND ROSE FOR WASP

THE LENGTH OF EACH STEM REPRESENTS THE PROPORTION
OF TIME THAT THE WIND COMES FROM THAT DIRECTION.

WIND FREQUENCY ANALYSIS

1. Winds are measured continuously and their direction and speed are then averaged each hour. The tables show, for each month and/or for the year as a whole:-

- a. The number of hours with the speed and direction in various categories.
- b. This number expressed as a percentage.

2. The period of the analysis is normally 10 years or longer and is shown at the top of the table. Therefore the hourly winds in all the January's (for example) in the period are summarised in the 'January' tables. The percentage frequency table is then a good guide to 'average' conditions in that month.

3. Wind directions are measured to the nearest 10 degrees from True North and relate to the direction from which the wind is blowing. For example :

Direction 360 degrees = wind blowing from North
Direction 090 degrees = wind blowing from East
Direction 180 degrees = wind blowing from South
Direction 270 degrees = wind blowing from West

Normally the size of each wind direction sector (350 - 010 , 020 - 040 etc) is 30 degrees, but other ranges can be used.

4. Normally, the speed ranges (1 - 3 knots , 4 - 6 knots , 7 - 10 knots etc) correspond to Beaufort Forces 1 , 2 , 3 etc , but other ranges can be used.

For converting speeds in knots to other units , the following relationship may be used :

1 knot = 0.515 m/s = 1.15 mph = 1.85 km/h

The following applies to the percentage frequency tables only

5. Adding the columns of the above table **VERTICALLY** gives the percentage amount of time in the month with winds from the stated directions.

6. Adding the columns of the above table **HORIZONTALLY** gives the percentage amount of time in the month with winds from the stated speed ranges.

7. 0.00 = less than 0.005
but
0.0 = zero

8. The vertical and the horizontal totals are correct but the sums of the individual values may not agree exactly due to the nearest decimal point.

BEAUFORT SCALE

Specification and Equivalent Mean* Wind Speeds on Land

Force	Description	Specifications for Use on land	Equivalent Speed at 10 m above ground			
			Knots Mean	Limits	Miles per hour Mean	Limits
0	Calm	Calm; Smoke rises vertically	0	<1	0	<1
1	Light Air	Direction of wind shown by smoke drift, but not by wind vanes	0	1-3	2	1-3
2	Light Breeze	Wind felt on face, leaves rustle, ordinary vane moved by wind	5	4-6	5	4-7
3	Gentle Breeze	Leaves and small twigs in constant motion: wind extends light flag	9	7-10	10	8-12
4	Moderate Breeze	Raises dust and loose paper; small branches are moved	13	11-16	15	13-18
5	Fresh Breeze	Small trees in leaf begin to sway crested wavelets form on inland waters	19	17-21	21	19-24
6	Strong Breeze	Large branches in motion; whistling heard in telegraph wires; umbrellas used with difficulty	24	22-27	21	25-31
7	Near Gale	Whole trees in motion; inconvenience felt when walking against wind	30	28-33	35	32-38
8	Gale	Breaks twigs off trees; generally impedes progress	37	34-40	42	39-46
9	Strong Gale	Slight structural damage occurs (chimney pots and slates removed)	44	41-47	50	47-54
10	Storm	Seldom experienced inland; trees uprooted; considerable structural damage occurs	52	48-55	59	55-63
11	Violent Storm	Very rarely experienced accompanied by wide spread damage	60	56-63	68	64-72
12	Hurricane	---	---	>64	---	>73

* There are no equivalent scales for gusts, although in open, level situations maximum gusts are typically 1.6 times the mean speeds.

EXPLANATION OF THE WIND ROSE

The booklet consists of 17 roses - one for each month, one for each season, and one for the year as a whole. Over a ten year period some 87,000 hourly observations of wind speed and direction are used to compile these diagrams.

North is at the top of the page as you read it. There are 12 arms coming from the central circle of the diagram, each representing a 30 degree segment of wind direction. The length of the arm is proportional to the amount of time, in hours, the wind blew from that particular segment. The different thicknesses of the line represent different wind speed classes: the key is at the top left hand corner.

Wind directions are expressed in degrees from true north and represent the direction from which the wind is blowing.

Speeds are in knots (nautical mph), with 1 knot = 1.15 mph, or 0.515 metres per second.

The centre circle gives information about the number of observations used in compiling each rose, the percentage of the time when the winds were calm and the percentage of the time with variable winds.

Other types of wind analysis can be presented in this form, including different wind direction sectors or different speed classes. Gust winds or 10 minute ("spot") winds can also be used. If these or any other types of analysis are of interest, please contact us at the following address.

For Further Information please contact

Pauline Tonkinson (0344 856207) Heather Stevens (0344 856965)
Fax 0344 854906
Environmental Consultancy Services (Air Pollution)
Meteorological Office Commercial Services
Room JG9 Johnson House
London Road
Bracknell
Berkshire
RG12 2SY

HOURLY MEAN WINDS AT ALL MONTHS
 PERIOD: 01 1981 - 12 1990 (C) CROWN COPYRIGHT 1991

MAP SHOWING STATIONS WITH UPPER-AIR DATA

KEY:

- Main UK stations.
Radiosonde ascent at 00 GMT and 12 GMT giving pressure, temperature, humidity, wind speed and direction observation by electronic means. Radio ascents at 06 GMT and 18 GMT giving upper-wind observations by tracking of a free balloon by electronic means (radio or radar)
- ▲ As above but intermittent recordings
- ▨ HL of ground >200m

NOTES ON THE UNITS USED FOR ASCENTS AND PILOTS

STANDARD LEVELS

PRESS	Calculated pressure above mean sea level in millibars
HEIGHT	Calculated height above mean sea level in metres
TEMP	Calculated temperature in degrees C
DEWPT	Calculated dew point in degrees C
RH	Calculated relative humidity in percent
HMR	Calculated humidity mixing ratio in grams of water per kilogramme of air
DDD	Calculated wind direction degrees true
FFF	Calculated wind speed in knots

SIGNIFICANT TEMPERATURES

PRESS	Observed pressure in millibars
HEIGHT	Calculated height above mean sea level pressure
TEMP	Observed temperature in degrees C
DEWPT	Calculated dew point in degrees C
RH	Calculated relative humidity in percent
HMR	Calculated humidity mixing ratio in grams of water per kilogramme of air

SIGNIFICANT WINDS

PRESS	Observed pressure in millibars
HEIGHT	Calculated height above mean sea level in decimetres
DDD	Observed wind direction in degrees true
FFF	Observed wind speed in degrees true

STANDARD WINDS

PRESS	Calculated pressure above mean sea level in millibars
DDD	Calculated wind direction in degrees true
FFF	Calculated wind speed in knots

INVERSION FREQUENCY ANALYSIS

Normally air temperature decreases with height however sometimes it may increase with height over some depth. This state is called an "inversion". A volume of air displaced upwards (or downwards) in an inversion soon finds itself cooler and denser (or warmer and lighter) than it's environment and is forced back to it's original level, thus inhibiting vertical mixing.

Pollutants are therefore trapped by inversions unless they are contained in very hot plumes that can either totally or partially penetrate inversions of limited depth. Inversions tend to form either when the air near the ground is colder than the air above or at the top of the turbulent "boundary layer". Inversions can also occur at any height due to the motion of large-scale air masses.

Section 1 Number of inversions within a given Layer above the ground. Each inversion within a Layer being described in terms of thicknesses and temperature differences.

Layers (in metres) used are At Surface, Above Surface to 100, 101 to 200, 201-300, 301-400, 401-500, 501-600, 601-700, 701-800, 801-1000, all elevated inversions above surface, all surface and elevated inversions.

Thicknesses (in metres) used are 1-60, 61-120, 121-180, 181-240, 241-300, 301-360, 361-420, 421-500, over 501.

Temperature (deg C) differences are 0.1-0.5, 0.6-1.0, 1.1-1.5, 1.6-2.0, 2.1-3.0, 3.1-4.0, 4.1-5.0, 5.1-6.0, over 6.0.

Section 2 Mean annual number of temperature inversions expressed as percentage of number of soundings. Thicknesses and Layers as above.

Section 3 Mean seasonal number of temperature inversions expressed as percentage of number of soundings. Thicknesses and Layers as above.

INVERSION FREQUENCY ANALYSIS (Continued)

DESCRIPTION OF ANALYSIS METHOD

- 1) Standard and significant level data from each radiosonde sounding have been merged to produce a dataset of Temperature (deg C) versus Height (metres) above mean sea level.
- 2) The Temperature / Height data set has been examined from the surface upwards to identify temperature inversions where the rate of change of temperature with height is positive.
- 3) The base of the inversion is defined as the first level at which the temperature gradient becomes positive.
- 4) Any isothermal layer which occurs is included within the inversion.
- 5) The top of the inversion is defined as the level at which the temperature gradient becomes negative again.
- 6) The analysis has been restricted to heights below the 700 mb level (2500 - 3000 m). Inversions associated with the tropopause and stratosphere have not been analysed.
- 7) Radiosondes used in the United Kingdom have very sensitive temperature sensors. Consequently a large number of weak inversions have been analysed as well as a smaller number of strong inversions.
- 8) On many occasions there are more than one inversion in a single sounding. There are frequently two inversions and sometimes as many as four or more inversions in a single sounding.
- 9) The number of inversions has been expressed as a percentage of the number of soundings, therefore on some occasions the total percentage exceeds 100 percent.
- 10) Missing values in the columns headed " MEAN TEMPERATURE DIFFERENCE " are indicated by 99.9.

Missing values in the rows labelled " MEAN HEIGHT DIFFERENCE " are indicated by 999.9.

INVERSION FREQUENCY ANALYSIS

Example of Section 1

STATION NAME - WMO NUMBER -
 PERIOD ANALYSED - 0 1 1 1988 TO 23 31 12 1988

NUMBER OF INVERSIONS AS A FUNCTION OF THICKNESS AND TEMPERATURE DIFFERENCE

TIME OF DAY. 00 GMT

LAYER IN WHICH INVERSION BASE OCCURS (METRES). AT SURFACE

THICKNESS OF INVERSION (METRES)	TEMPERATURE DIFFERENCE THROUGH INVERSION (DEG C)								OVER	ALL
	0.1	0.6	1.1	1.6	2.1	3.1	4.1	5.1	6.0	
1- 60	48	27	12	7	3	4	1	0	0	1
61- 120	30	26	11	3	6	4	1	3	0	84
121- 180	20	20	10	3	8	1	1	0	2	65
181- 240	10	5	2	3	1	1	0	1	3	26
241- 300	2	4	2	5	3	1	2	1	1	21
301- 360	1	0	2	0	2	1	0	0	5	11
361- 420	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	3
421- 500	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	3
OVER 501	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	3
ALL	114	83	40	22	23	12	7	5	13	319

TIME OF DAY. 00 GMT

LAYER IN WHICH INVERSION BASE OCCURS (METRES). ABOVE SURFACE TO 100

THICKNESS OF INVERSION (METRES)	TEMPERATURE DIFFERENCE THROUGH INVERSION (DEG C)								OVER	ALL
	0.1	0.6	1.1	1.6	2.1	3.1	4.1	5.1	6.0	
1- 60	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
61- 120	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
121- 180	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
181- 240	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
241- 300	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
301- 360	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
361- 420	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
421- 500	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
OVER 501	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ALL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

TIME OF DAY. 00 GMT

LAYER IN WHICH INVERSION BASE OCCURS (METRES). 0101-0200

THICKNESS OF INVERSION (METRES)	TEMPERATURE DIFFERENCE THROUGH INVERSION (DEG C)								OVER	ALL
	0.1	0.6	1.1	1.6	2.1	3.1	4.1	5.1	6.0	
1- 60	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
61- 120	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
121- 180	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
181- 240	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
241- 300	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
301- 360	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
361- 420	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
421- 500	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
OVER 501	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ALL	3	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	5

INVERSION FREQUENCY ANALYSIS

Example of Section 2

STATION NAME - WMO NUMBER -
 PERIOD ANALYSED - 0 1 1 1988 TO 23 31 12 1988

MEAN ANNUAL NUMBER OF TEMPERATURE INVERSIONS EXPRESSED AS PERCENTAGE OF NUMBER OF SOUNDINGS
 TIME OF DAY. 00 GHT

LAYER IN WHICH INVERSION BASE OCCURS (METRES). AT SURFACE											
THICKNESS OF INVERSION (METRES)	TEMPERATURE DIFFERENCE THROUGH INVERSION (DEG C)										MEAN TEMP DIFF (DEG C)
	0.1	0.6	1.1	1.6	2.1	3.1	4.1	5.1	OVER	ALL	
1- 60	13.2	7.4	3.3	1.9	0.8	1.1	0.3	0.0	0.3	28.3	0.9
61- 120	8.2	7.1	3.0	0.8	1.6	1.1	0.3	0.8	0.0	23.1	1.1
121- 180	5.5	5.5	2.7	0.8	2.2	0.3	0.3	0.0	0.5	17.9	1.4
181- 240	2.7	1.4	0.5	0.8	0.3	0.3	0.0	0.3	0.8	7.1	1.9
241- 300	0.5	1.1	0.5	1.4	0.8	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.3	5.8	2.2
301- 360	0.3	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.5	0.3	0.0	0.0	1.4	3.0	4.0
361- 420	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.3	0.8	4.9
421- 500	0.3	0.3	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.8	1.1
OVER 501	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.8	1.4
ALL	31.3	22.8	11.0	6.0	6.3	3.3	1.9	1.4	3.6	87.6	1.4
MEAN THICKNESS (M)	98.2	107.8	121.8	154.9	161.6	122.0	245.9	150.4	250.8	123.3	

LAYER IN WHICH INVERSION BASE OCCURS (METRES). ABOVE SURFACE TO 100											
THICKNESS OF INVERSION (METRES)	TEMPERATURE DIFFERENCE THROUGH INVERSION (DEG C)										MEAN TEMP DIFF (DEG C)
	0.1	0.6	1.1	1.6	2.1	3.1	4.1	5.1	OVER	ALL	
1- 60	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	99.9
61- 120	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	99.9
121- 180	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	99.9
181- 240	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	99.9
241- 300	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	99.9
301- 360	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	99.9
361- 420	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	99.9
421- 500	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	99.9
OVER 501	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	99.9
ALL	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	99.9
MEAN THICKNESS (M)	999.9	999.9	999.9	999.9	999.9	999.9	999.9	999.9	999.9	999.9	

LAYER IN WHICH INVERSION BASE OCCURS (METRES). 0101-0200											
THICKNESS OF INVERSION (METRES)	TEMPERATURE DIFFERENCE THROUGH INVERSION (DEG C)										MEAN TEMP DIFF (DEG C)
	0.1	0.6	1.1	1.6	2.1	3.1	4.1	5.1	OVER	ALL	
1- 60	0.5	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.8	0.2
61- 120	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0
121- 180	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	99.9
181- 240	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	1.6
241- 300	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	99.9
301- 360	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	99.9
361- 420	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	99.9
421- 500	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	99.9
OVER 501	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	99.9
ALL	0.8	0.3	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.4	0.4
MEAN THICKNESS (M)	370.7	37.0	3.0	9.0	99.0	999.0	999.0	99.0	99.0	3.2	

INVERSION FREQUENCY ANALYSIS

Example of Section 3

STATION NAME - WMO NUMBER -
 PERIOD ANALYSED - 0 1 1 1988 TO 23 31 12 1988

MEAN SEASONAL NUMBER OF TEMPERATURE INVERSIONS EXPRESSED AS PERCENTAGE OF NUMBER OF SOUNDINGS
 TIME OF DAY. 00 GMT
 LAYER IN WHICH INVERSION BASE OCCURS (METRES). AT SURFACE

SEASON WINTER (DEC, JAN, FEB)

INVERSION THICKNESS (METRES)	TEMPERATURE DIFFERENCE THROUGH INVERSION (DEG C)									
	0.1	0.6	1.1	1.6	2.1	3.1	4.1	5.1	OVER	ALL
	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	6.0	
1- 60	9.9	7.7	0.0	1.1	1.1	1.1	0.0	0.0	1.1	22.0
61- 120	4.4	12.1	4.4	1.1	1.1	2.2	0.0	1.1	0.0	26.4
121- 180	6.6	5.5	3.3	1.1	2.2	1.1	0.0	0.0	1.1	20.9
181- 240	1.1	2.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	4.4
241- 300	0.0	1.1	1.1	3.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.5
301- 360	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	2.2
361- 420	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
421- 500	0.0	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1
OVER 501	2.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.2
ALL	24.2	29.7	8.8	6.6	5.5	4.4	0.0	1.1	4.4	84.6

SEASON SPRING (MAR, APR, MAY)

INVERSION THICKNESS (METRES)	TEMPERATURE DIFFERENCE THROUGH INVERSION (DEG C)									
	0.1	0.6	1.1	1.6	2.1	3.1	4.1	5.1	OVER	ALL
	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	6.0	
1- 60	14.4	8.9	2.2	3.3	0.0	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	30.0
61- 120	14.4	3.3	3.3	1.1	2.2	0.0	1.1	0.0	0.0	25.6
121- 180	3.3	5.6	4.4	0.0	2.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	15.6
181- 240	6.7	2.2	0.0	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	10.0
241- 300	1.1	2.2	0.0	1.1	1.1	0.0	1.1	1.1	0.0	7.8
301- 360	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1
361- 420	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
421- 500	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
OVER 501	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
ALL	41.1	22.2	10.0	6.7	5.6	1.1	2.2	1.1	0.0	90.0

SEASON SUMMER (JUN, JUL, AUG)

INVERSION THICKNESS (METRES)	TEMPERATURE DIFFERENCE THROUGH INVERSION (DEG C)									
	0.1	0.6	1.1	1.6	2.1	3.1	4.1	5.1	OVER	ALL
	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	6.0	
1- 60	19.6	8.7	4.3	0.0	1.1	1.1	1.1	0.0	0.0	35.9
61- 120	10.9	7.6	2.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	20.7
121- 180	8.7	3.3	1.1	1.1	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	15.2
181- 240	1.1	1.1	1.1	0.0	1.1	1.1	0.0	1.1	0.0	6.5
241- 300	0.0	1.1	1.1	0.0	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.3
301- 360	0.0	0.0	2.2	0.0	0.0	1.1	0.0	0.0	1.1	4.3
361- 420	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	0.0	0.0	1.1
421- 500	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
OVER 501	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	0.0	0.0	1.1
ALL	40.2	21.7	12.0	1.1	4.3	3.3	3.3	1.1	1.1	88.0

SEASON AUTUMN (SEP, OCT, NOV)

INVERSION THICKNESS (METRES)	TEMPERATURE DIFFERENCE THROUGH INVERSION (DEG C)									
	0.1	0.6	1.1	1.6	2.1	3.1	4.1	5.1	OVER	ALL
	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	6.0	
1- 60	8.8	4.4	6.6	3.3	1.1	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	25.3
61- 120	3.3	5.5	2.2	1.1	3.3	2.2	0.0	2.2	0.0	19.8
121- 180	3.3	7.7	2.2	1.1	3.3	0.0	1.1	0.0	1.1	19.8
181- 240	2.2	0.0	1.1	2.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.2	7.7
241- 300	1.1	0.0	0.0	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.1	0.0	1.1	6.6
301- 360	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.3	4.4
361- 420	0.0	0.0	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	2.2
421- 500	1.1	0.0	0.0	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.2
OVER 501	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
ALL	19.8	17.6	13.2	9.9	9.9	4.4	2.2	2.2	8.8	87.9